

doi:10.5281/zenodo.16929846

Managing Executive-Legislative Working Relationship For Good Governance And Service Delivery In Nigeria

Olutunbosun Sunday Emmanuel ODUSANYA¹ & ²CHUKE, P. I. & ³UROYE, Augustine

¹Department of Politics and Administration
University Africa, Lagos, Nigeria
olatunbosunodusanya@gmail.com
08033932174/08082779974
ORCID:0009-0008-8066-1525

^{2,3} Department of Political Science and Public Administration
Novena University, Ogume, Nigeria

ABSTRACT

With the return to democratic rule in 1999, it was widely anticipated that democracy would reverse the trend of economic decline and curb socio-political instability. However, more than a decade later, the nation continues to grapple with severe socio-economic and political challenges. Many analysts have linked these problems to the recurring executive-legislative conflicts. Nevertheless, it is generally acknowledged that fostering a cooperative working relationship between the executive and the legislature is vital for effective governance and improved service delivery. Anchored on systems theory, this paper highlights the necessity of managing the executive-legislative relationship. It concludes that while the executive arm is primarily responsible for policy formulation, evaluation, and implementation to achieve developmental goals, the legislature is charged with enacting laws and ensuring they function as instruments of social cohesion. The interaction between the two arms is, therefore, pivotal to sustaining good governance in a democratic system. Dialogue, rather than confrontation, is essential in resolving their differences, as persistent conflicts often stall policy formulation and hinder implementation.

Keywords: Democracy, Efficiency, Performance, Social Contract, Political Stability.

INTRODUCTION

Since independence, Nigeria has grappled with the legacy of the British parliamentary system in which members of the legislature were assigned ministerial portfolios under the principle of collective responsibility. From that era, the need for synergy between the executive and legislature became evident. However, the conflicts and rancor that plagued the First and Second Republics eventually paved the way for prolonged military rule. This denied both arms of government the time and institutional maturity necessary to cultivate a stable working relationship. To address these shortcomings, the framers of the 1979 Constitution adopted the American-style presidential system, anchored on separation of powers, and introduced a bicameral legislature consisting of the Senate and the House of Representatives. Due to the dominance of the ruling National Party of Nigeria (NPN), executive-legislative conflicts during the Second Republic were relatively limited.

The legislature of the aborted Third Republic made little impact, largely because of General Ibrahim Babangida's authoritarian hold on power and his annulment of the June 12, 1993 presidential election. As Amadi (2005:4) argued, the Senate under Babangida was rendered ineffective, not because politicians lacked will, but because the regime imposed extensive restrictions that paralyzed legislative functions—a situation with lasting implications.

With the return to civilian rule in 1999, expectations were high that past mistakes would guide executive–legislative relations. However, during President Olusegun Obasanjo's administration, persistent friction was evident in the frequent changes of leadership in the National Assembly, particularly in the Senate. Efforts by the legislature to amend or challenge executive bills were often perceived as defiance, reflecting a lingering military mentality resistant to democratic norms. Since 2007, however, relations between the two arms have gradually stabilized. Leadership in both chambers has become less volatile, and threats of impeachment, once commonplace, have largely disappeared—though occasional conflicts remain.

At all levels of government, the three arms—executive, legislature, and judiciary—though distinct in functions, must interrelate to provide effective checks and balances. The executive sets the pace of governance and development, while the legislature, as the custodian of national sovereignty, enacts laws and provides oversight.

At the grassroots, local governments were established as the third tier of government to bring governance closer to the people. Modeled after the presidential system, local councils have an executive arm headed by a chairman, assisted by a vice chairman and supervisory councillors, while the legislative arm consists of elected councillors. Ideally, cooperation between the two arms is essential for effective service delivery. In practice, however, many councils are plagued by conflicts, with governance often overshadowed by parochial politics. Local government administration is frequently run as personal estates by political elites, leading to inefficiency, mismanagement, and instability (Oyeleye, 2003; Omo, 1994).

From this backdrop, the need to foster a workable synergy between the executive and legislature at all levels cannot be overstated. Such collaboration is crucial for peace, security, effective governance, and the institutionalization of global best practices.

Conceptual Clarifications

The **executive** runs the machinery of government, formulating policies and ensuring implementation, while the **legislature** enacts laws and ensures societal cohesion (Onyebuchi, 2013; Andre, 1994). Both arms are interdependent, and neither can function effectively in isolation. Modern legislatures, however, have expanded beyond law-making to include oversight and accountability functions (Jain, 1975; Ekhaton, 2003; Bade, 2000).

In Nigeria's presidential system, the executive includes the President, cabinet, governors, commissioners, and local government chairmen. Good governance, as defined by Anazodo, Igbokwe-Ibeto & Nkahi (2015), entails accountable institutions, respect for civil liberties, economic growth, poverty reduction, and strong social policies. Service delivery, as Akhakpe (2014) notes, represents the quality and efficiency of public services, which remains a pressing challenge in Nigeria due to corruption, poor recruitment policies, and decayed infrastructure.

Theoretical Orientation: Systems Theory

Systems theory, which emphasizes the interdependence of subsystems within a whole, is highly relevant to executive–legislative relations. A healthy relationship entails harmony and cooperation among subsystems toward achieving collective goals, while antagonism or dysfunction in any subsystem undermines the system as a whole. Although systems theory has been criticized as overly mechanical, it underscores the need for collaboration between the executive and legislature in addressing governance, democratization, human rights, security, and economic development.

The Nexus Between Federalism and Executive–Legislative Relations

Federalism is essentially about devolution of power from the center to states and local governments. The 1999 Constitution emphasizes separation of powers across all levels of government to prevent tyranny. Following Montesquieu’s principle, checks and balances were enshrined to ensure accountability, with each arm capable of curbing the excesses of the other. As the U.S. Federalist No. 51 famously noted, “ambition must be made to counteract ambition.”

Areas of Collaboration

1. **Law-making:** Although the legislature has primary responsibility for law-making, the executive participates through assent, making collaboration essential.
2. **Public Finance Management:** Budget preparation belongs to the executive, but approval and oversight rest with the legislature, ensuring that spending reflects citizens’ needs.
3. **Oversight:** The legislature ensures transparency and accountability through investigations, hearings, and scrutiny of executive actions (Verney, 1969; Stapenhurst in Fashagba, 2011).
4. **Appointments:** While the executive nominates key officials, the legislature confirms them to ensure competence and credibility.

Challenges

Persistent conflict arises from power struggles, overlapping functions, weak understanding of constitutional roles, executive dominance, corruption, poor leadership, and inadequate conflict resolution mechanisms (Momodu & Matudi, 2013). Despite constitutional provisions for good governance, the prevalence of poverty, corruption, and mismanagement indicates a disconnect between constitutional ideals and governance reality.

The Way Forward

Good governance requires both the executive and legislature to prioritize public service delivery. Legislatures must strengthen law-making, representation, and oversight roles, while the executive must focus on policy formulation and implementation. Dialogue should replace confrontation, with both arms respecting constitutional boundaries and the principle of separation of powers. Capacity-building programs in conflict resolution and governance are also necessary.

CONCLUSION

The relationship between the executive and legislature is central to democratic governance in Nigeria. While the executive formulates and implements policies, the legislature enacts laws and provides oversight, and the judiciary interprets them. Cooperation, rather than conflict, is essential for peace, security, and development. For democratic institutions to thrive, both arms must base their relationship on trust, respect, and mutual accountability, adhering strictly to constitutional provisions. As Taylor (1996) argues, achieving balance between the executive and legislature is critical for efficient state administration and sustainable democracy.

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